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+91-94155 78129 | +91-79051 90645

serfoundation123@gmail.com | serresearchfoundation.in

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Authored by

Ms. Baby Zoofishan

Research Scholar

Department of B.Ed./M.Ed. Faculty of Education and Allied Sciences
MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh

Dr. Pratibha Sagar

Assistant Professor

Department of B.Ed./M/Ed, Faculty of Education and Allied Sciences
MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh.

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A STUDY OF EFFECT OF FAMILY CLIMATE ON MENTAL HEALTH OF B.ED. TEACHER-TRAINEES

Ms. Baby Zoofishan*
Dr. Pratibha Sagar**

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to find out the effect of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees. Descriptive survey method was used for this study. Sample consisting 160 B.Ed. teacher-trainees was selected by using random sampling technique from 4 B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district. Family climate scale developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K. Chadha (2019) and mental health inventory developed by C.D. Aagshe and R.D. Helode (2008) used for data collection. Data was analyzed using Mean, S.D. and ANOVA (F-test). Finding reveals that not significant interaction effect of different dimension of family climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees except only one dimension i.e. active-recreational orientation.

Keywords : Family Climate, Mental Health, B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Introduction :

Family is the first social climate where individual fulfils his/her physical, mental and cultural needs. Family interaction plays an important role in the development of an individual. The healthy functioning of these interaction patterns enhances mental health. Thus we can say that family climate moulds the behaviour, personality, attitude, aptitude, self-esteem and mental health of an individual (Kaur *et al.*, 2015). Webster dictionary (2004) defines 'family' as a group of persons, consisting of parents and their children. It also defines 'climate or environment' as the aggregate of all external and internal conditions affecting the existence, growth and welfare of organisms.

Mental health is an important determinant of one's integrated personality and balanced behaviour, identified on the basis of the level of his/her adjustment to own self, others and environment (Kaur *et al.*, 2015). A mentally healthy individual can adjust properly with environment, family and contribute for the society's progress and betterment (Lewkan, 1993). Mental health is the

adjustment of human being with the world and also with one another to the maximum of effectiveness and happiness. It is the ability to maintain socially considerate behaviour, a happy disposition, an even temper and alert intelligence (Meninger, 2004).

Family climate plays an important role in every field of student's life. In this specific context the present research will undertaken to specifically provide empirical answers of these questions like what is role of family climate on mental health. A study was conducted on mental health of secondary school students in relation to family climate by Singh and Devi (2018). Findings of this study revealed that a significant positive relationship of mental health with family climate. Similarly, Shivanae (2011) reported significant difference of family climate and mental health of tribal and urban secondary school students. In a study, Kumar and Chaturvedi (2017) observed that mental health and occupational aspiration of college students have positive and significant relationship. Review of related literature reveals that various studies had been conducted family climate and

*Research Scholar - Department of B.Ed./M.Ed. Faculty of Education and Allied Sciences, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh

**Assistant Professor - Department of B.Ed./M/Ed, Faculty of Education and Allied Sciences, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh.

mental health in relation to various variables such as academic achievement, anxiety, life-satisfaction, occupational aspiration, intelligence, adjustment, adolescent-period etc. But it was found that no study has been conducted effect of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees. Hence the researcher has decided to undertake, the study of effect of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Objectives of the study :

1. To study the effect of different dimensions of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
2. To explore the effect of different dimensions of family climate on mental health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
3. To detect the interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Hypothesis of the study

1. There is no significant effect of different dimension of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

2. There is no significant effect of different dimensions of family climate on mental health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
3. There is no significant interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Research Design & Methodology :

The researcher used descriptive survey method. Population of the present study consists of all the teacher-trainees of B.Ed. colleges affiliated to M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly. Sample of 160 teacher-trainees of 4 B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district selected with the help of simple random sampling techniques. **Family Climate Scale (FCS)** developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K.Chadha(2019) and **Mental Health Inventory (MHI)** developed by C.D. Aagshe and R.D. Helode (2008) were used for the study. Data were analysed using Mean, S.D., and F-test (ANOVA).

Data analysis and interpretation :

Hypothesis 1 : There is no significant effect of different dimension family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table 1.1: Descriptive statistics of mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Dimensions of Family Climate	Family climate Group	N	Mean	S.D.
1. Cohesion	High FC	20	22.85	4.380
	Average FC	111	22.29	3.679
	Low FC	29	20.00	3.443
2. Expressiveness	High FC	41	21.78	3.135
	Average FC	111	21.95	4.096
	Low FC	8	22.75	3.370
3. Conflict	High FC	9	25.00	4.796
	Average FC	116	22.00	3.772
	Low FC	35	20.97	3.374

4. Acceptance and Caring	High FC	8	23.88	5.222
	Average FC	112	22.02	3.780
	Low FC	40	21.35	3.592
5. Independence	High FC	7	24.57	3.599
	Average FC	67	22.63	4.163
	Low FC	86	21.20	3.388
6. Active-Recreational Orientation	High FC	35	24.06	3.531
	Average FC	92	21.43	3.841
	Low FC	33	21.12	3.333
7. Organization	High FC	59	21.92	4.087
	Average FC	54	22.78	3.446
	Low FC	47	21.02	3.756
8. Control	High FC	22	23.50	3.789
	Average FC	81	22.19	3.905
	Low FC	57	21.00	3.520

One way ANOVA has been performed for testing the hypothesis-1. The result of ANOVA for mental health have been shown in table-1.2.

Table 1.2: summary of ANOVA (Effect of different dimension family climate on mental- health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.)

Dimensions	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean of Squares	F-Ratio	Results
1.	Cohesion	104.096	2	52.048	3.693*	Significant
2.	Expressiveness	14.794	2	7.397	0.496	Non-Significant
3.	Conflict	79.186	2	39.593	2.800	Non-Significant
4.	Acceptance and Caring	70.511	2	35.256	2.419	Non-Significant
5.	Independence	111.066	2	55.533	3.898*	Significant
6.	Active-Recreational Orientation	94.352	2	47.176	3.628*	Significant
7.	Organization	109.931	2	54.965	3.828*	Significant
8.	Control	140.154	2	70.077	4.949**	Significant

* Significant at 0.05 level

** Significant at 0.01 level

The above table shows that the null hypothesis w.r.t. dimensions cohesion, independence, active recreational orientation, organization and control dimensions are rejected. Type of family climate (high, average and low) of B.Ed. teacher-trainees have different mental health in cohesion, independence, active recreational orientation, organization and control dimensions. Similarly the null hypothesis of

expressiveness, conflict and acceptance & caring dimension are accepted and alternative hypothesis are rejected. Type of family climate (high, average and low) of B.Ed. teacher-trainees do not effect mental health in expressiveness, conflict and acceptance & caring dimension.

Hypothesis2: There is no significant effect of different dimensions of family climate on mental health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table 2.1: Descriptive statistics of mental health of male and female B.Ed.teacher-trainees.

Dimensions of Family Climate	Family climate Group	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.
1.COHESSION	High FC	M	6	23.33	4.502
		F	14	22.64	4.483
	Average FC	M	28	22.14	4.080
		F	83	22.34	3.559
	Low FC	M	10	20.90	3.957
		F	19	19.53	3.151
2.EXPRESSIVENESS	High FC	M	3	20.70	2.312
		F	5	22.13	3.314
	Average FC	M	31	22.39	4.485
		F	80	21.78	3.952
	Low FC	M	10	22.67	4.509
		F	31	22.80	3.114
3.CONFLICT	High FC	M	3	22.67	5.508
		F	6	26.17	4.46
	Average FC	M	30	22.33	4.003
		F	86	21.88	3.705
	Low FC	M	11	21.00	4.171
		F	24	20.96	3.043
4. Acceptance and Caring	High FC	M	2	27.50	0.707
		F	6	22.67	5.574
	Average FC	M	33	21.91	3.987
		F	79	22.06	3.715
	Low FC	M	9	21.22	4.177
		F	31	21.39	3.480
5.Independence	High FC	M	2	22.50	3.536
		F	5	24.20	3.962
	Average FC	M	22	22.55	4.426
		F	45	22.67	4.079
	Low FC	M	20	21.10	3.582
		F	66	21.23	3.355

6.Active-Recreational Orientation	High FC	M	11	22.09	3.419
		F	24	24.96	3.263
	Average FC	M	18	23.00	4.678
		F	74	21.05	3.542
	Low FC	M	15	20.80	3.649
		F	18	21.39	3.127
7 .organization	High FC	M	15	21.80	3.590
		F	44	21.95	4.281
	Average FC	M	15	23.87	3.720
		F	39	22.36	3.289
	Low FC	M	14	20.29	4.358
		F	33	21.33	3.497
8. control	High FC	M	8	24.25	3.105
		F	14	23.07	4.178
	Average FC	M	19	22.79	4.674
		F	62	22.00	3.662
	Low FC	M	17	20.12	2.977
		F	40	21.38	3.698

Two way ANOVA has been performed for testing the hypothesis-2. The result of ANOVA for mental health have been shown in table-2.2

Table 2.2 summary of ANOVA (Effect of different dimensions family climate on mental-health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Dimension	Source	Sum of squares	Df	Mean squares	F-Ratio	Result
Cohesion	Gender	7.972	1	7.972	0.566	N.S.
Expressiveness	Gender	1.271	1	1.271	0.085	N.S.
Conflict	Gender	13.361	1	13.361	0.945	N.S.
Acceptance and caring	Gender	23.891	1	23.891	1.639	N.S.
Independence	Gender	1.328	1	1.328	0.093	N.S.
Active recreational orientation	Gender	7.044	1	7.044	0.542	N.S.
Organization	Gender	0.329	1	0.329	0.023	N.S.
Control	Gender	1.447	1	1.447	0.102	N.S.

The above table shows that null hypothesis of all dimensions of family climate with respect to gender are accepted. It can be concluded that mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees do not influence the different dimensions of family climate with respect to gender.

Hypothesis3 : There is no significant interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Two way ANOVA has been performed for testing the hypothesis-3. The result of ANOVA for mental health have been shown in table-3.1

Table 3.1 summary of ANOVA (interaction effect of different dimensions of family climate and gender on mental-health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.)

Dimensions	Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean of squares	F-Ratio	Result
1.	Cohesion*gender	13.224	2	6.612	0.469	N.S.
2.	Expressiveness *gender	23.629	2	11.814	0.793	N.S.
3.	Conflict*gender	28.664	2	14.332	1.013	N.S.
4.	Acceptance and Caring*gender	35.586	2	17.793	1.221	N.S.
5.	Independence *gender	2.767	2	1.384	0.097	N.S.
6.	Active-Recreational Orientation *gender	119.582	2	59.791	4.599*	Significant
7.	Organization *gender	35.099	2	17.549	1.222	N.S.
8.	Control*gender	34.801	2	17.400	1.229	N.S.

The above table shows that the null hypothesis of interaction effect of different dimension of family climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees except only one dimension i.e. active-recreational orientation.

Conclusions : cohesion, independence, active recreational orientation, organization and control dimensions of the family climate affected the mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

References :

- Balilashak,N., Safavi, M. & Mahmoudi, M. (2010). Comparative assessment of mental health

of gifted and average students of junior high school. *Procedia-Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 5, 2027-2033.

- Biswas, J. (2017). *A study mental health, test anxiety and academic overload in adolescent of working and non-working mothers* (Ph.D. Thesis). Calcutta University, Calcutta.
- Kaur, M., Dhillon, S. S. & Kaur, K. (2015). A study of relationship of family environment with mental health of adolescent of Sirsa district. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(19), 472-475.

- Kaur, M. (2017). *Life satisfaction of undergraduate students in relation to their mental health, emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence* (Ph.D. Thesis). Punjab University, Chandigarh.
- Kumar, S. & Chaturvedi, S. (2017). A study of influence of mental health on occupational aspiration of college students in district Haridwar. *Shrinkhla Ek Shodhparak Vaicharak Patrika*, 5(4).
- Lewkan ,P. V. (1993). *Mental hygiene and hygiene in public health*. Urlando: F.L. Harcourt Brace.
- Meninger, K. A. (2004). *The human mind*. New York: Mcgrow-Hill.
- Shivane ,D. (2011). A study the family environment and mental health of the tribal and urban secondary students. *Indian Streams Research Journal*, 16(5), 187-190.
- Sing, A. & Devi, S. (2018). Mental health of secondary school students in relation to family climate. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 8(4), 853-861.
- *Webster Dictionary (2004)*. The new international Webster's comprehensive dictionary, 247 & 457. Trident Press International, U.S.A.

